

The AI Bubble: Formation, Current Market Dynamics, and Future Implications

Mr. Dnyandeep G. Khawale¹, Mr. Anurag A. Bharati² and Ms. Priyanka N. Chandawar³

M.Sc. Student, Department of Computer Science, Dr. S.C Gulhane Prerna College of Commerce, Science and Arts, Nagpur, India¹

M.Sc. Student, Department of Computer Science, Dr. S.C Gulhane Prerna College of Commerce, Science and Arts, Nagpur, India²

Assistant Professor, Dr. S.C Gulhane Prerna College of Commerce, Science and Arts, Nagpur, India³
dnyandeepkhawale55@gmail.com¹, personalsanurag@gmail.com², priyanchandawar@gmail.com³

Abstract: *This paper will examine the systemic risks of the Artificial Intelligence market upswing of 2022-2026 and the economical mechanism underlying it. While Generative AI is very useful technologically, its present market valuation seems to have broken away from its realized revenue, supported by a "circular economy" of infrastructure investment. This paper will analyze "round-tripping" of capital flow between cloud hyperscalers, hardware manufacturers, and AI startups. It will also study the systemic risks imposed by debt-financed data center expansion, the rapidly evolving "patience deficit" among investors, and the physical resource limitations that will serve as a ceiling for further expansion—specifically, shortages of energy and materials (such as silver and high bandwidth memory). Ultimately, we'll compare this market cycle to the 2000 dot-com bubble. We argue that while a bubble exists, its nature and origin have led to tangible assets rather than "vaporware". It seems likely that an inevitable "deflationary correction" will be needed for market value to stabilize with unit economics.*

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, AI Bubble, Market Analytics, Information Technology, Circular Economy, Data Centre.*

1. Introduction

A. Market Context

Since the introduction of ChatGPT at the end of 2022, the technology sector's financial market has seen a significant reorientation toward Generative AI. Initially focused on software development, the sector has now evolved into a capital-intensive "Infrastructure Phase", with immense demand for high-performance computing hardware. Major tech companies and venture capitalists have pledged more than \$1 trillion in predicted capital expenditure (CapEx) to construct data centers and buy Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) [1]. Market participants are increasingly concerned about the widening gap

between this hardware spending and the revenue generated by end-user applications, signaling a potential overheated market.

B. Problem Definition

The core issue facing this market is the "Revenue Gap", defined as the substantial difference between the total investment made in hardware for the AI industry and the actual annual revenue it generates. Reports suggest that industry organizations have invested at such an extent on the hardware that the AI industry needs to recover about \$600 billion annually to achieve a break even. In reality these organizations are not even generating a quarter of the above said revenue annually [2]. The mentioned issue gradually increases due to the "Price For perfection

model” which assumes immense growth, while ignoring real world limits, during valuation [3]. The valuation of the investors that invest and the AI startups that receive that investment boosts both their revenue publicly without creating realistic value from the market due to “Round-Tripping” [4].

C. Contribution to Literature

We focus to research and understand the structural working of the AI Bubble and deep dive into the circular investment pattern between the “Hardware Providers”, “Cloud Infrastructure Firms” and “AI Startups”. Also, we are going to overview the risks that arise from building data centers on borrowed money and investors that are now being cautious and pulling back their investments and how the real world limits largely affects the growth of the industry [5][6]. We also want to prove that judging by the previous “dot-com” global crash of the 1990s, there is an deflation adjustment of the market going to occur to correct the actual market values and the capacities of the organizations involved in this bubble.

2. Bubble Formation Mechanics

The present AI Market economics differs greatly from previous market trends mostly because of “Round Tripping”.

A. Cyclical Capital Flows and "Round-Tripping"

"Circular financing" or "round-tripping" is a major representation of the present AI market.

1. *The Feedback Loop*: This is a closed circular loop between hardware manufacturers, cloud providers and AI Startups where the money keeps on circulating between the same companies. What happens is that the hardware manufacturers invest in AI Startups, these startups then buys cloud computing services from cloud providers using the money invested by the hardware manufactures. Now the cloud providers use the same money they received from the AI Startups to buy even more hardware from the same hardware manufactures that invested in the AI Startup [4].

2. *The “Car Dealer” Theory*: This theory explain how a broken car is given to a “Mechanic” for repairs at an “X” amount of money. The “Mechanic” then uses the same “X” amount of money to buy the car from the Owner. In reality transaction was shown but no Money was moved [7].

3. *Real-World Example*: When hardware manufacturers invest in CSP with contracts that state if the CSP is unable to accomplish the agreed upon target sales then the hardware manufacturer will buy back its own products. This de-risks the purchase for the CSP and artificially inflates the vendor's shipment volumes [8].

B. Infrastructure-Led Growth Strategy

In stark contrast to the "software-first" growth of the mobile internet era, the AI boom is defined by an "Infrastructure-First" approach, with a belief that market demand will follow investment.

1. *FOMO Catalyst*: Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) is a primary driver of corporate strategy. Industry leaders have stated that they would rather risk over-investing in GPU clusters than under-investing, leading to a "race condition" where compute capacity is stockpiled without immediate need [9].
2. *CapEx vs. Utilization*: Financial reports from 2024 and 2025 show that hyperscalers are spending significantly more on data center CapEx than ever before-over \$100 billion annually for some[1]. However, this capacity is being built in anticipation of future applications that have not yet emerged, raising concerns of an inventory glut if demand stagnates.

C. Vendor Concentration and Interdependency

The market is heavily dependent on a single hardware architecture (GPU), creating a single point of failure.

1. *Revenue Concentration*: A large share of the hardware vendor's revenue comes from a few major hyperscalers. A liquidity crisis at any of these large entities or failure of a major AI model developer could have immediate ripple effects upstream to the hardware vendor, breaking the "circular" flow of cash [7].
2. *The deal between Open AI and Oracle*: The Billion-dollar deal that happened between these two giants of the industry is one of such examples where they are valued on the future basis rather than the current revenue, they are capable of generating [8].

3. Financial structure and systemic risks

The ability of current AI market to sustain itself is questionable as it's mostly sustained because of the big funding. In this part of the paper, we will see all such factors such as Return on investments, risks of debts and shifting of investors' interest.

A. Valuation Metrics and the "Patience Deficit"

The AI companies market has always been valued as a product that is "priced for perfection" where investors expect fast growth in the future to cover or explain the losses they are currently facing. But that Patience also runs out at some point, because of which investors are now punishing companies spending too much money that does not give an instant profit or the fast growth [10].

1. *Reality of "Zero Percent Returns"*: A recent study done by MIT says that most the companies or investor investing in the AI market has seen zero percent returns on their investment, this number goes as high as 95% [11]. This shows us the real gap between original value and its capability.
2. *Gap in Revenue*: The valuation at which the current Ai market is at shows an annual revenue that is not possible in reality. Companies will require to earn at least \$600 billion to even reach the break even point for the \$1 trillion they have spent on the hardware, where as their actual revenue is not even half of it [2]. This gap in the

revenue shows us that the actual focus of this companies is on building infrastructure rather than running a profitable service.

B. Banking Sector Exposure and Debt Securitization

The biggest problem that arises due to this AI bubble is the participation of the banking sector as they provided loans for building the infrastructures.

1. *Securitizing Leases*: : Cloud providers and Data centers are taking large amounts of secured loans to put money into expansion. This includes selling leases backed by the lease contracts and their payment they will receive from Ai startups to the banks and pension funds [4].
2. *Systemic Risk*: This system bears the same risk as the 2008 crisis. If AI startup fails to sustain itself along with making money and cannot afford to pay for its leases, the assets which were valued because of this will fall down, putting large impact on the banks and retirement funds [12]. This can start bigger problems where a tech decline will affect the general economy.

C. Market Fragility and Capital Rotation

The stock market is too much weak because it is concentrated.

1. *Concentration Risk*: A small group of companies, "The Big Seven" are controlling the movement of S&P 500's. Changes in the valuation of these seven companies will have a great impact on the whole market [3].
2. *"Risk-Off" Trend*: Due to the ongoing problems, the capital invested in "Risk On" Stocks like Tech is being pulled back and moving towards defensive "Risk Off" assets. This shows the loss of confidence on the current valuation stability and shift towards commodities as risk management [5].

4. Physical and market constraints

Problems such as “Energy Shortages” and “Raw Material Limitations” are creating tight physical limitations on the growth of AI Infrastructure.

A. The Energy and Hardware Wall

The biggest challenge for setting up an AI Data center at a larger scale is the lack of sufficient electric supply.

1. **Power Grid Limitations:** Even though large tech companies are investing around 400 billion dollars in setting up Data centers but major tech regions are lacking to provide support over the increase in electricity, as a result of this expensive GPU Chips remain unused due to the lack in power supply [8].
2. **Memory Supply Chain Bottlenecks:** While GPUs are becoming more available, the supply of High Bandwidth Memory (HBM) and CoWoS (Chip-on-Wafer-on-Substrate) is limited and scarce. Manufacturers are booked till 2027. This scarcity make the cost of server RAM go up, impacting the profitability of AI startups [13].

B. The "Silver Flip" and Commodity Impact

During 2025, the global value of “Silver” was higher than the combined value of Nvidia and all the Cryptocurrencies [14], because it is important element for making semi-conductors and as there were export restrictions on silver. This shows how the digital world directly affects the resources.

1. **The "Silver Flip":** December 2025 was the month where investors took out their money from risky assets such as crypto and tech stocks and put that money in a much safer asset such as commodities as they are seen as a safe investment [14].
2. **Safe Haven Rotation:** Investors say that even if AI Companies valuation drops, the demand for Silver will remain strong as it is a very important semiconductor for making a lot of electronics and semiconductors. Thus, investors started moving their money more towards commodities

such as silver in preparation for the “AI Bubble” to burst.[5] [6].

5. Technological limitations

While external factors pose challenges, internal technological barriers are also questioning the vision of ubiquitous Artificial General Intelligence (AGI).

A. The Breakdown of Scaling Laws

The long-held belief that increasing parameters, compute, and data yields proportional intelligence gains ("Scaling Laws") is now being challenged.

1. **Diminishing Returns:** As AI models scale from billions to trillions of parameters, the marginal improvement in reasoning ability is shrinking while training costs skyrocket. This raises concerns about the economic viability of training "frontier models," as the cost may exceed the revenue from their marginal utility [12].
2. **"Baby Weight" Analogy:** The current strategy is being compared to the flawed assumption that a baby who doubles its weight in 18 months will eventually reach a trillion pounds. The lack of truly "emergent properties" in recent models indicates that brute force computation may no longer be the key to greater intelligence [12].

B. The "Last Mile" Paradox and Reliability

AI models' inability to achieve 100% reliability creates a "Last Mile" problem, hindering their use in critical, high-stakes applications.

1. **The Outlier Problem:** As statistical engines, deep learning models struggle with "outlier" events, situations not present in their training data. Self-driving cars, for example, often fail to navigate novel hazards [12].
2. **Hallucination Persistence:** LLMs continue to generate fabricated information ("hallucinations"), making them unsuitable for sensitive fields like law, medicine, or finance without human oversight. This means AI will likely function as a "Co-pilot" rather than an

"Autopilot", thus limiting its impact on labor costs and the Total Addressable Market (TAM) [15].

C. Data Exhaustion

The exponential hunger for training data has collided with the finite supply of high-quality human knowledge.

1. *The "Finite Internet"*: Researchers and industry leaders agree that the internet has been largely "exhausted" of its high-quality public text data.
2. *Synthetic Data Risks*: To compensate, developers are turning to synthetic (AI-generated) data, but this risks "Model Collapse"-a degenerative process where models trained on their own output become increasingly inaccurate [12].

6. Future Projection: Correction vs. Consolidation

The History of market and current situation shows the future of the AI market and how it might look.

A. The Dot-Com Parallel: A Comparative Analysis

Mostly compared to the Dot-com bubble, the current AI bubble has major differences.

1. *Asset Reality*: The "Dot-com Bubble" of 2000's involved many organizations with no actual existing product, either the product was an imagination or unfinished, these organizations were known as "Vaporware". The AI Bubble involves the "Asset-Rich" Companies that own real and valuable assets such as computing hardware and GPU's which carries values even if the market goes down[16]. The Real problem is going to be encountered by the smaller companies who are developing AI tools using already existing AI Models, such companies are known as "Wrapper" companies, and they are at the most risk as they don't have any valuable infrastructure to rely on if the market were to collapse [17] [18].

2. *Earnings Resilience*: Unlike the revenue-less startups of 1999, major AI ecosystem players (e.g., NVIDIA, Microsoft) generate substantial free cash flow. Emerging markets, particularly India, have shown flexibility, with price based on earnings disappointments rather than pure current hype [17]. This means that when the market correction happens the companies which own AI computing infrastructure such as chips and GPU's maybe survive the market correction but the "Wrapper Companies" which rely on AI models for the operations are likely to collapse [18].

B. Scenarios for Market Stabilization

We can predict two possible paths for market:

1. *Scenario A: The "Deflationary Bust" (Hard Correction)*: In this scenario there is sudden market collapse which is caused by an unexpected event such as a regulatory action or a physical limitation. To explain this with an explain is when a lot of GPU's are produced but suddenly the demand is cut short then the hardware prices are likely to decrease causing companies that borrowed money to invest in infrastructure to face the most damage. This is also a good time for young companies to the enter the market as the infrastructure is cheap at that moment [5] [8].
2. *Scenario B: The "Co-Pilot" Equilibrium (Soft Landing)*: The market correction will reset the AI markets value and it will be seen as a tool that helps humans to work better [15].

7. Conclusion

The recent "AI Boom" in between 2022 and 2026 is a very good example of "Technological Decoupling" that shows how an organizations market value grows much faster that the actual profits earned by that organization. Another primary instability indicator that exists is the "Revenue Gap" which is the difference between the amount of money invested in infrastructure and the annual revenue that is generated. The AI Bubble exists today majorly

because of "Round-Tripping" which is a tight closed financial loop that inflates the revenue of the cloud providers and AI Startups and other organizations that are involved in this loop. This AI system that exists today is a very fragile system that includes various physical limitations that are being neglected today, thus we would like to conclude by stating that the market is going to experience a correction phase which will shift the focus of the market towards a more cautious investment.

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